

GENDER AND LANGUAGE ATTITUDES TOWARDS PUNJABI: A DOMAIN-BASED ANALYSIS

Raza-E-Mustafa^{*1}, Syed Tahir Ul Amin², Mahnoor Ghani Sheikh³

^{*1}Assistant Professor, Department of English, University of Gujrat,

^{2,3}Assistant Lecturer, Department of English, University of Gujrat

¹razaemustafa@uog.edu.pk, ²tahir-ul-amin@uog.edu.pk, ³mahnoor.sheikh@uog.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Raza-E-Mustafa

Abstract

Punjabi, despite being the largest language spoken in Pakistan, continues to have a marginal status in the country due to its use in informal domains. Females' contribution towards shaping the attitudes in a certain language is significant. The study tried to find out if gender plays any role in shaping attitudes towards Punjabi by using Fishman's (1972) classification of Domains into five types, namely family, friendship, education, relationships and transactions to determine domains of language use and Rosenberg and Hovland's (1960) Tripartite Model of Language Attitudes as the theoretical framework for determining attitudes towards Punjabi. Thirty males and thirty females who identified themselves as ethnic Punjabis were asked to respond to a language attitudes Likert Scale questionnaire. The results showed that the females did indeed have a negative attitude towards Punjabi language, thus corroborating the initial hypothesis of the study. However, the age of the participants and their educational level had no bearing on the attitudes of Punjabis towards the Punjabi language. The study proved that gender plays an important role in shaping the attitudes towards a certain language.

INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt that most of the people living in Pakistan speak Punjabi language. (Rahman 2003). However, it faces a unique position in Pakistan. Although it is spoken by a vast majority of the country, yet it remains one of the most marginalized languages of the country. Schwieter (2008) believes that language represents speakers and speakers represent their language, but according to Rahman (2010) the speakers of Punjabi have played a role in marginalizing it by being ashamed of speaking it. This stigmatization of the language has led to the Punjabi-speaking families speaking Urdu as Motherese with their young kids. The current situation entails a diminished use of Punjabi language in the years to come due to non-use of this language by the next generations. One of the

issues, therefore, which needs immediate attention, is the role of women in stigmatization of the Punjabi language. Females, being mothers and sisters have significant impact on the next generation in the language choices. This paper tries to find out what attitude the females have towards Punjabi language and what can be the implications of their attitude for the future of Punjabi language in Pakistan.

2. Literature Review

Despite the fact that many languages are spoken in Pakistan, only 7.57 percent people speak Urdu as a mother tongue. (Rahman 2003). The official language of the country is English due to its British colonial heritage (ibid).

Jaspal and Coyle (2010) explored the identity and social mobility components of language attitudes among Punjabi speakers in Pakistan and diaspora communities. They discovered that children from economically upwardly mobile families usually discourage the use of Punjabi as it is perceived as a barrier to academic and career achievement. This conforms Bourdieu's (1991) linguistic capital theory, which highlights the manner in which language varieties become depreciated or appreciated based on the symbolic power they wield within specific social fields.

However, there has been rejuvenation of Punjabi language, especially in cultural and online spaces. The growth of Punjabi music, poetry, and drama particularly via channels like YouTube and social media—has helped instill pride among the younger generations (Hashmi, 2020; Shackle, 2007). Certain schools and civil society groups have also made attempts to enhance Punjabi language education and literacy.

Punjabi, despite being the largest language of the country, continues to be marginalized (Rahman 2003). One of the reasons for the marginalization of Punjabi is its use only in informal situations where friends and family members interact with one another freely. (Mansoor, 1993; Zaidi, 2010; Rahman, 1996 and 2002; Imtiaz-Asif, 2005). Despite being the majority language of the country as spoken by the largest proportion of the language, Punjabi is still treated as a minority language (Zaidi 2011). However, Bhatt and Mahboob (2008) claim that the idea of minority language is problematic as a language cannot be termed as being minority or majority language without taking into account its functional and sociolinguistic status in a certain community. They cite the example of Punjabi whose functions are limited to informal and domestic domain only. Din, Khan and Iqbal (2011) call the domains in which Urdu, English and Punjabi are used as “multiple nested triglossia” (p. 9). The table below shows the percentage of speakers of major languages in Pakistan according to Census 2001 and Census 2011:

Table 1: Population by Mother tongue

Language	Census 2001	Census 2011
Punjabi	44.15	38.78
Pashto	15.42	18.24
Sindhi	14.10	14.57
Siraiki	10.53	12.19
Urdu	7.57	7.08
Balochi	3.57	3.02
Others	4.66	6.12

Source: Pakistan Bureau of Statistics

According to the above table, the Punjabi language shows a remarkable decline in its usage over the period of ten years. While most languages have retained more or less the same number of speakers, Punjabi has shown a significant drop among people speaking Punjabi as their mother tongue. This trend shows the tendency of the younger generation to switching away from Punjabi and towards other languages especially Urdu. According to Rahman (2001) Punjabi is usually spoken at home and in informal domains, but in formal domains like political speeches or serious philosophical discussions

Urdu is used and for writing both Urdu and English are used.

Fishman (1972) defines a domain as “ building of sociocultural principles that are not found in daily conversation, to establish relationship between the speakers and the concerned population including different institutions of a society and the people of that locality in such a way that certain behaviors and patterns of individuals can be distinguished from each other ” (p. 20). He concludes that the main factors influencing the concept of domain are topic, role relation, and locale. He is of the opinion that

topic operates as a regulator of language where a lot of languages are spoken. He quotes example of such people who change their language according to their addressee's language while discussing certain topics. Obiols (2002) defines attitude as our evaluative disposition towards things. Ryan et. al (1982) define language attitudes as "cognitive and behavioural index which evaluates reactions of certain speakers effectively." (p. 7). However, we have to acknowledge that observing language attitudes is significant because other than predicting linguistic behaviors and the patterns of choosing one language over other languages, it can also help us in determining speakers' loyalty towards a certain variety and language prestige (Obiols, 2002).

It is clear beyond doubt that females involve prestigious varieties of language in their speech (e.g. Hoare, 2000; Labov, 1972; Trudgill, 1974) and they are always interested in learning a foreign language (e.g. Sung & Padillar, 1998; Nadeem, Shafqat & Mustafa, 2025). Piller & Pavlenko (2008) believe that men prefer to use the vernacular language, because the 'street language' is supposed to carry greater covert prestige and is associated with masculinity (p. 502). Giddens (1989) considers gender as the psychological, social and cultural differences between males and females whereas sex refers to the biological differences between men and women. James (1996), while explaining the relationship between language and gender, suggests that social factors need to be taken into account. The relative power between males and females, their social networks and social status etc. are some of them.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Fishman's (1972) framework of domains of language use has been used as a guide to determine the domains of the use of Punjabi language by males and females. Fishman (1972) has divided the language use into five domains i.e. family, friendship, education, relationships and transactions. These domains are "commonly associated with a particular variety or language" (Fishman 1972, p. 44). He describes them in terms of the setting, the subject, and the participant roles. Domains are frequently described as formal or informal, for example, family and friends or business. The dominant language is frequently perceived as

being associated to the language use in more formal domains and the minority language to the more casual ones in multilingual contexts.

According to Fishman (1972), topic, role relation, and locale are the variables that have an impact on the concept of domain. In multilingual circumstances, he claims, that subject may control how language is used. It is a fact that often we switch from our native language to the addressee's language while discussing certain topics. The focus of this study is to know the attitude of males and females towards Punjabi language in the above domains of language use. The study uses Rosenberg and Hovland's (1960) Tripartite Model of language attitudes as a guide for analyzing attitudes towards Punjabi language. The Tripartite Model divides attitudes into three main categories i.e. cognitive, behavioural and affective. Cognitive attitudes refer to thinking about the language and in the language, the behavioral component of attitudes is concerned about doing and affective component deals with the emotional aspect of attitudes.

2.1.1 Cognitive Attitude

People's beliefs about thing constitute their cognitive attitude. Beliefs can be both positive or negative. Positive attitude is the result of positive thoughts and negative attitude is the result of negative thoughts. Gardener (1985) states that "The target of cognitive component is to analyse the individual belief system" (p. 8). Personal attitude is "an evaluative reaction to some referent or attitude object, inferred on the basis of the individual's beliefs and opinions about the referent" (Gardner, 1985, p. 9).

Pratkanis (2014) is of the view that "the cognitive category consists of responses that reflect perceptions of and information about, the attitude object" (p. 243). A person's beliefs, either positive or negative about anything, constitute his/her attitudes.

2.1.2 Affective attitude

Emotions and feelings about a language are included in affective attitude. Azjen (2005) states that the "verbal responses in medical profession can be considered either admiration or rejection" (p. 5). For example, a person who feels good after medical care of nurses and doctors will show his positive attitude

towards the medical profession, but another person who is not satisfied with the medicine recommended by the doctor will show his negative attitude about doctors and the medical profession (Azjen, 2005). A person can show his attitude through gestures, body movement and facial expressions.

2.1.3 Behavioral attitude

Behavior is the third component of attitude. It concerns with actions towards any language. If a person has a favorable behavior towards a language, he will prefer to learn or speak that language more often. Azjen, (2005) believes that “we can control or supervise all the activities of people in all the circumstances” (p. 5). Those who have a negative attitude towards medical profession might refuse to go to the doctor. Our negative behavior about any object will create anxiety and fear.

3. Methodology

The study uses a descriptive and analytical approach and falls under the quantitative paradigm. The quantitative data collected through a language attitudes questionnaire has been analyzed using the SPSS software. The following sections explain in detail the processes of sample selection and tool construction.

a. Sample Selection

Thirty men and thirty women of varying ages were selected from Gujrat area. The ages of the participants varied from 16 to 44 with average age being 20.3 years. There were two groups of participants according to their age. One group consisted of ages from 16 to 24; whereas, the second group consisted of ages from 25 to 44. The sample also had a degree of variability regarding their educational qualification. 10 men and 12 women had a master degree; 14 men and 13 women had a BA/BSc degree and 6 men and 5 women had educational qualification of intermediate or less.

b. Tool Construction

A questionnaire comprising 20 items from 5 domains as specified by Fishman (1972) and constituting of the items based on Rosenberg and Hoveland’s (1960) Tripartite Model of Language Attitudes was designed. Five-point Likert scale was used for the ease of analysis. The questionnaire was piloted and was found reasonably reliable ($\alpha=0.63$). The reliability of the subsets of the questionnaire relating to each domain also showed similar consistency as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Internal Reliability Statistics

Domain	Number of items	Cronbach’s alpha (α)
Family	4	0.65
Friendship	4	0.60
Education	4	0.61
Relationships	4	0.64
Transactions	4	0.64

(Values rounded off to two decimal points)

4. Data Analysis

In order to compare the attitude of the males and females towards Punjabi language, an independent samples t-test was conducted. The test revealed that

there was a significant difference between the attitudes of the males and females towards Punjabi language. Table 3 shows the results of the test.

Table 3: Independent Samples T-Test

Groups	N	X [̄]	SD	T
Male	30	79.171	4.38	0.0012*
Female	30	68.743	6.47	

P < 0.05

With P=0.002, the difference between the attitudes of males and females was significant at 95% confidence level (P < 0.05).

The difference of attitudes of males and females in each domain is represented in Table 4.

Table 4: Domain-wise/Gender-wise Attitude

Domain	Male	Female
Family	16.03	12.67
Friendship	18.23	17.51
Education	12.92	10.11
Relationships	15.38	14.79
Transactions	16.61	13.35
Total	79.17	68.74

Another independent samples t-test was conducted to find the difference of attitudes between the two age groups. Since the number of participants in the two age groups was different, the mean score was used in the tests instead of the total score.

Table 5: Independent Samples T-Test

Groups	N	X'	SD	T
16-24	38	4.17	1.02	6.738
25-44	22	4.46	1.17	

P < 0.05

The results showed that although the mean score of the age group 25-44 was slightly higher than the group 16-24, but the difference was not deemed statistically significant by the SPSS.

In order to find out the difference among the educational qualification of the respondents, One-Way ANOVA was conducted. Again the mean score was used instead of the total score because of the unequal number of participants in different groups.

Table 6: One-Way ANOVA

	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between groups	4.04	2	8.674	1.937	1.031
Within groups	4.18	12	2.261		
Total	4.23	14			

Table 7: Descriptives

	N	X'	SD	Std. Error	95% confidence interval for mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
MA/MSc	22	4.14	0.98	0.5783	2.3487	3.3365	2.00	5.00
BA/BSc	27	4.17	1.02	0.0963	2.8327	2.7342	1.00	5.00
FA/FSc	11	4.15	1.03	0.8912	2.1529	2.4218	1.00	5.00

The results showed that there was no significant difference in the attitude towards Punjabi language among the respondents having different qualifications. Even their mean scores (X') showed little discernable variance.

5. Conclusion

The results showed a marked difference in the attitude of males and females. However, there was no difference in the attitude of the respondents on the basis of their academic qualification or age. The domain-wise results (As shown in Table 4) showed that both male and female respondents scored significantly higher in family, friendship and transactions and scored the lowest in education domain. This proved Rahman's (2001) assertion that Punjabi is used in informal domains and not for educational purposes. However, the age of the respondents and their educational qualifications had no bearings on their attitude towards Punjabi language. In the light of the results it can be argued that with a slightly less positive attitude of the females towards Punjabi language, the overall attitude towards Punjabi is getting negative gradually.

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